

THE FUTURE OF ENVIRONMENTAL LITIGATION IN NIGERIA: Trends and Challenges

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1.0. ABSTRACT

A few decades after the Koko Waste incident, came the realization that litigation could be used as a tool to combat a major aspect of environmental issues. Thus, this paper examines the future outlook of environmental litigation in Nigeria, by evaluating emergent trends such as the mobilisation of the steady increase in climate change lawsuits, holding high-risk industries accountable for damages caused and enforcement of human rights in relation to the environment to achieve environmental justice. It also assesses key challenges environmental litigation in Nigeria is currently faced with. By discussing the historical development of Nigeria's environmental background and studying landmark cases, this paper concludes with recommendations to significantly assist the improvement of environmental litigation in Nigeria.

2.0. INTRODUCTION

The saying 'Rome was not built in a day' specifically refers to the development and emergence of the Nigerian environmental litigation system. Prior to the Koko waste incident, which brought environmental challenges to the spotlight and opened the eyes of the government to the threats that environmental pollution posed, Nigeria practised simple modes of waste disposal and removal from the society. This was typically carried out through teamwork and community efforts by participating in clean-up activities and expurgations. In simpler words, members of the community were guided by mutually accepted rules and regulations to appropriately dispose refuse in certain designated spots that had been earlier selected by the authorities of such communities.

This mode of environmental sanitation was before the persistent increase in population and the gradual advancement of industrialization, which resulted to concomitant effects such as steady progression in hazardous wastes, carbon emissions, climate change and a few others. However, it was soon realised that Nigeria was not the only country experiencing the adverse impacts of these emerging environmental issues. It was as a result of all these, that the United Nations took the initiative and held a world conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm, 1972.¹⁶⁴ The aim of the conference was to address attendant global environmental concerns and proffer solutions to the growing threats that the future of sustainability was faced with.

The Nigerian government, however, did not take action or cognizance of the measures that were put in place at the conference until the Koko waste incident in 1988. The fact of the case was, that an Italian businessman illegally dumped over 2000 drums of toxic waste into the river of the small fishing community.¹⁶⁵ That is, it was only after a small fishing community suffered the consequences of the government's inaction and ignorance towards environmental protection, that they sprung into action which led to the proclamation of the first ever environmental legislation in Nigeria; Federal Environmental Protection Agency Decree (FEPA Decree 1988 repealed).¹⁶⁶ The Decree then established the Federal Environmental Protection Agency and vested it with, the authority and responsibility to regulate and protect the environment.

In 1999, FEPA and other environmental bodies were merged to form the Federal Ministry of Environment (FME now known to be "Federal Ministry of Environment, Housing and Urban

¹⁶⁴ United Nations, 'United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (5-16 June 1972) Stockholm,' <<https://un.org>>

¹⁶⁵ United Nations Environment Programme, 'Bamako Convention: Preventing Africa from Becoming a Dumping Ground for Toxic Waste, published 30 Jan 2018, <<https://unep.org>>

¹⁶⁶ F, Doherty, 'History of FEPA in Nigeria,' Published 15 June 2016, <<https://fumilayodoherty.blogspot.com>>

Development). This was soon later replaced with the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) which was created by the NESREA Act of 2007.¹⁶⁷ This body was tasked with the duty of setting environmental standards and enforcing compliance with the provisions of international treaties of which Nigeria was a signatory to. Over time, other legislation such as the National Policy on Environment, Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) 1992, were integrated into the Nigerian environmental legal frameworks.

With the Koko waste incident, came the realization that culprits of environmental pollution should be held accountable for their actions and thus, the idea of litigation as an instrument to combat environmental issues was conceived. Hence, the establishment and enactment of these legislation only served as a cherry on top a cake. Because with the ratification of these laws, the judicial arm could now intervene to enforce rights, address civil wrongs and hold violators of environmental regulations accountable for the damages their actions might have caused to certain aggrieved individuals or the public at large.

3.0. EMERGING TRENDS IN ENVIRONMENTAL LITIGATION

3.1. Climate Litigation

Whilst climate litigation otherwise known as climate change litigation may be considered to be an emerging aspect of environmental law, climate change in itself has been an environmental threat, the human race has been faced with since the early 19th century.¹⁶⁸ Presently, according to the 2020 Status review by the Global Climate Litigation Report, the report shows that “*as of the 1st of July 2020, the number of cases has doubled with at least 1,550 climate change cases filed in 38 countries.*”¹⁶⁹

Climate litigation cases majorly revolve around suits against the government for apathetic behaviour towards addressing climate change and its attendant effects, holding corporations responsible for hazardous activities affecting the climate by demanding adaption and remediation costs and enforcing rights to a good climate.

3.2. Human Rights Approaches and Environmental Justice

¹⁶⁷ National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency Act, 2007 (No 25 of 2007), <<https://www.ecolex.org>>

¹⁶⁸ Fourier J, 'Remarques Generals Sur Les Temperatures Du Globe Terrestre et des EspacesPlanestaires',Annales de Chimie et de Physique (1824), Wikipedia, <<https://en.m.wikipedia.org>>

¹⁶⁹ UN Environment Programme, 'Global Climate Litigation Report: 2020 Status Review,' Published 26 January 2021, <<https://unep.org>>

Another trend in Nigeria's environmental litigation system is the use of human rights approach to attain environmental justice. In the popular United States case of *Juliana v United States*,¹⁷⁰ where 21 young Americans brought an action against the United States Government arguing that the actions of the government violated their rights to a stable climate system, according to a District Judge, Ann Aiken who ruled that "a climate system capable of sustaining human life" was a fundamental right under the United States Constitution.¹⁷¹ Although the case was dismissed, it did not erase the environmental awareness raised and impact made by such legal actions. This goes to show that the public is interested and actively involved in the sustainability and protection of their environment.

Another landmark case is *Urgenda Foundation v State of the Netherlands*,¹⁷² in this case, an action was brought against the Netherlands government stating that the government's inactions by failing to meet up with a carbon emission goal was jeopardizing the human rights of Dutch citizens as provided for by the European Union Laws and it was the first successful climate litigation case.¹⁷³

3.3. Demanding Accountability from Corporate Bodies

The Nigerian government in an attempt to foster accountability has also enacted laws and regulations for this purpose. These laws which include Federal Environmental Protection Agency Act 1992, Federal Ministry of Environment Act 1999, National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act 2007, Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provisions) Act, 2004 set guidelines for ensuring accountability and compliance amongst industrial companies. An emphasis was placed in Principle 26, part E of the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance, 2018 to ensure the reduction of environmental harm¹⁷⁴, as failure to comply by these set rules has led to the undeserving consequences on both human health and the community at large.

Echefu and Akpofure (2002) critically stated the inactive nature of environmental impact assessment in the daily operation of companies¹⁷⁵. **Ladan (2009) on the other hand**, lamented of the inefficiency of NESREA; the foremost environmental legislation in Nigeria in ensuring and maintaining compliance.¹⁷⁶

¹⁷⁰ *Juliana v United States*, 947 F.3d 1159 (9th Cir.2020)

¹⁷¹ J. Sutter, 'Climate Kids take on the Feds,' CNN, 9 March 2016, Wikipedia, <<https://en.m.wikipedia.org>>

¹⁷² *Urgenda Foundation v State of the Netherlands*, ECLI:NL:HR:2019:2007

¹⁷³ *Urgenda Foundation v State of Netherlands* (2015) HAZA C/09/00456689 (24 June 2015), Environmental Law Alliance Worldwide, Published 24 June 2015, <<https://elaw.org>>

¹⁷⁴ Nigerian Code of Governance, 2018, Part E, Principle 26 (FRCN, 15 Jan 2019), <<https://pwcnigeria.typepad.com>>

¹⁷⁵ Echefu N. and Akpofure E, 'Environmental Impact Assessment in Nigeria: Regulatory Background and Procedural Framework,' (2002)

¹⁷⁶ Ladan M. T, Review of NESREA Act 2007 and Regulations 2009-2012: A New Dawn in Environmental Compliance and

However, reluctance of these bodies to abide by the rules, the complexity of these laws, lack of implementation plans and inadequate oversight can be curbed through the promotion of awareness to the society, creation of strategic agencies and initiatives like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and avoidance of ambiguity in enactment of laws.

4.0. KEY CHALLENGES FACING ENVIRONMENTAL LITIGATION

4.1. *Locus Standi*

The Cambridge dictionary defines Locus standi to mean “*the right or ability to bring a legal action to court of law or to appear in a court.*”¹⁷⁷ The rationale behind the locus standi principle in judicial proceedings is to ensure that meddlesome interlopers are not encouraged to interfere and only parties to a suit can appear before a court and obtain reliefs. In the past, the requisite before a person could bring an environmental action was that he or she must possess an ample degree of interest and this right must have been directly affected by the violation.

This soon became a serious setback, preventing individuals and small communities from bringing actions against environmental offenders because they did not have the legal standing to sue. However, this is no longer the case since it was realized that there were some third parties who had crucial interest in the protection of the environment and they could be exempted from the general rule. In the case of *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation*¹⁷⁸, the court held that non-governmental organizations have the locus standi to sue on the basis of public interest and environmental protection.¹⁷⁹ It was from here that Nigeria marked a paradigm shift in the locus standi rule which allowed only parties with sufficient interest to institute an action.

4.2. The Difficulty Proving Causation and Damages

One of the major complications persons experience while embarking on environmental litigation is difficulty in proving the determinant of the damages caused by actors of environmental degradation.

¹⁸⁰This is due to lack of financial resources to carry out assessments that would determine the causality and inability to provide sufficient proof to indict environmental offenders. This is mostly the case with

Enforcement in Nigeria. Law Env't and Dev. J. 2012; 8:116, <<https://www.sciepub.com>>

¹⁷⁷ Cambridge Online Dictionary, <<https://dictionary.cambridge.org>>, date accessed 7 May 2025

¹⁷⁸ Centre for Oil Pollution v Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation, 2019, 5 NWLR (Pt. 1666) 518

¹⁷⁹ B Ramos, 'Environmental Public Interest Litigation in Nigeria: The Paradigm Shift in COPW v NNPC (2019) 5 NWLR (PT. 1666) 518, Published 29 Jan 2020, <<https://papers.ssrn.com>>

¹⁸⁰ H. Mazeedah, 'Problem of Proof and Causation in Environmental Litigation in Nigeria,' Academia, <<https://academia.edu>>

high risk industries, who wield the financial capacity to mobilise the necessary technical instruments, experts and legal representatives to ensure that they are not found guilty.

4.3. Compliance with Court Judgments and Regulations.

Previously, several court decisions have been in favour of the aggrieved parties or affected communities. Adherence to these rulings has been a major obstacle in driving environmental justice. This is caused by several factors including implementation failure where necessary, environmental enforcement agencies such as NESREA are faced with financial and logistical constraints, bureaucracy or delay in judicial processes. Also, the unnecessary and cumbersome procedures where in some cases, appeal may need to be filed but the lengthy legal process might discourage aggrieved individuals or communities from seeking redress. Also, where the defendants are high risk industrial companies (mostly companies in the Oil and Gas Sector) whose interests benefit the government, enforcement of judgments tends to be difficult and the domestication of corrupt practices such as bribery, all of which undermines the integrity of the judiciary.

Additionally, multinational oil companies like Shell (SPDC) and Chevron which are often defendants (offenders) in environmental suits, often refuse to comply to court orders by pursuing endless appeals and at times, seek out-of-court settlements that further delays compliance. Also, lack of community empowerment where the plaintiffs (affected persons or communities) are often unable to hold violators accountable due to ignorance of their rights, limited access to legal aid as well as fear of retaliation has constituted other causes of noncompliance with court's judgements.

4.4. Jurisdictional Setbacks

Jurisdiction is seen as the authority given to a court by law to hear and determine matters or lawsuits. This is as well viewed as the competence to decide on a case. In the locus classicus case of *Madukolu v. Nkemdilim*,¹⁸¹ the elements of jurisdiction of a court include that it is properly constituted with respect to the number and qualification of its membership and that the subject matter of the action is within its jurisdiction.¹⁸² Section 8(f) of NESREA states that “*subject to the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, and in collaboration with relevant judicial authorities establish mobile courts to expeditiously dispense cases of violation of environmental regulations.*”

Although no court is bestowed with the exclusive jurisdiction to hear environmental cases, the Federal High Court and High Courts have jurisdiction to determine cases of such nature. For instance, there are

¹⁸¹Madukolu&Ors v Johnson Nkemdilim (1962) 2 SCNLR 341; (1962) 1 All NLR 587

¹⁸² Gabriel Madukolu&Ors v Johnson Nkemdili (1962) 2 SCNLR 341, Excerpt or Authority on Jurisdiction of Courts in Nigeria, <<https://crunchcaselaws.wordpress.com>

environmental courts in Cross Rier State to preside over the violation of environmental laws.¹⁸³ However, the condition precedents which were stated in *Madukolu v. Nkemdilim*¹⁸⁴ have become setbacks in enforcing a valid action. For instance, section 251 of the 1999 Nigerian Constitution¹⁸⁵ limited the jurisdiction of State High Courts in oil mining matters and this was strongly affirmed by the Supreme Court *Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria Limited v. Chief G.B.A. Tiebo and ORS*¹⁸⁶. Also, in *Asogwa v. Chukwu*¹⁸⁷, the court held that where there is failure to comply with the issuance of pre-action notice as prescribed by the law, the court will not assume jurisdiction. Jurisdiction has been used to hinder justice in some cases, and it is advisable to make provisions for environmental courts in order to address this issue.

6.0. CONCLUSION

The future of environmental litigation in Nigeria depends on both legislative reforms and judicial awakening. This enables the legislature to enact laws which cover environmental aspect and where the courts also move beyond compensatory justice to embrace ecological restoration. As climate pressures increase, Nigerian environmental litigation is set to be driven by a judiciary that recognizes the environment as a litigant with standing of its own.

6.0. RECOMMENDATION

In order to foster environmental justice and strengthen environmental litigation, it is necessary to enact clear legal frameworks that expressly recognize the right to a healthy environment as a fundamental human right. This also includes incorporating key principles such as sustainable development, the precautionary and the polluters pay principles. Judges and legal practitioners in the field of environmental law should be given training on environmental litigation by integrating indigenous ecological knowledge into legal reasoning. The establishment of specialized environmental courts is also important, as these courts will provide the exclusive jurisdiction, expertise and consistency needed to adjudicate complex environmental cases and suits effectively. Lastly, to ensure better court activism in environmental litigation and justice, the government should endeavour to provide a wider legal framework where climate risks and considerations can be incorporated and adopted.

¹⁸³ The (Special Courts) Designation Order 2016, Special Courts Department in Cross River State Judiciary, <https://www.judiciary.cr.gov.ng>

¹⁸⁴ (Supra)

¹⁸⁵ Chapter 7, Part 1, Section 252 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) Jurisdiction

¹⁸⁶ SPDC v Chief G.B.A. Tiebo&Ord (2005) 3-4 S.C 137, (2005) LPELR 3203 (SC), (2005) 9 NWLR (Pt 931) 439

¹⁸⁷ Asogwa v Chukwu (2003) 4 NWLR (Pt 811) 540 at 552